

**Reactivation of the Zic2-developmental axon guidance program
redirects regenerating visual axons in the adult CNS**

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ABSTRACT

Axon regeneration in the adult visual system is commonly achieved by enhancing intrinsic growth programs, yet regenerating axons frequently fail to navigate correctly at key decision points. This indicates that growth promotion alone is insufficient to restore precise connectivity. Here, we test whether reactivation of an embryonic guidance program can confer trajectory control to regenerating adult axons. We show that adeno-associated virus-mediated expression of the developmental transcription factor *Zic2* in adult retinal ganglion cells induces the expression of Eph receptors and β -catenin accumulation, reinstating sensitivity to midline repulsive cues. Notably, ephrinB2 and *Wnt5a*, guidance ligands critical during development, remain expressed at the adult optic chiasm. Whereas regenerating axons navigate stochastically at the chiasm under growth-promoting conditions, *Zic2* expression biases their trajectories away from the midline, redirecting them predominantly into the ipsilateral optic tract. These findings suggest that adult neurons retain a latent intrinsic competence, potentially supported by a permissive chromatin landscape, that allows developmental guidance programs to be re-engaged when appropriate transcriptional regulators are reinstated. Together, our results suggest that reinstating developmental identity modules can re-enable specific navigation decisions in regenerating adult axons, providing an entry point to engineer reconnection with greater precision.

INTRODUCTION

Restoring connectivity after central nervous system injury requires not only axon regrowth, but also the ability of regenerating axons to make appropriate navigation decisions. This requirement becomes particularly evident in long-range projection neurons, where axons must traverse complex environments and resolve multiple choice points in order to re-establish correct circuits. In the visual system, retinal ganglion cells (RGCs) extend long axons from the retina to central brain targets, and their failure to regenerate after optic nerve injury results in irreversible visual deficits in a range of pathological conditions^{1,2}. Over the past decade, substantial progress has been made in promoting axon regeneration in adult RGCs by manipulating intrinsic growth programs. Genetic and viral strategies targeting the mTOR and JAK/STAT pathways—often through conditional deletion of PTEN or activation of cytokine signaling—have demonstrated that adult RGCs retain a latent capacity for long-distance axon extension after injury^{3–6}. In parallel, circuit-based approaches have shown that increasing neural activity in retinorecipient targets can further promote long-distance regrowth and aspects of target-directed regeneration in the adult visual system^{7–9}. Together, these advances have shifted the prevailing view of CNS neurons from being intrinsically incapable of regeneration to being constrained by molecular and circuit-level programs that can be partially reversed.

However, enhancing axon growth alone has revealed an additional and persistent limitation. Regenerating RGC axons frequently display guidance errors along the visual pathway, including misrouting at the optic nerve head and the optic chiasm, and inappropriate projections to the wrong hemisphere or targets^{10–12}. These observations indicate that successful regeneration requires more than axon elongation: regenerating axons must also execute precise trajectory decisions to re-establish orderly and functionally meaningful circuits¹³.

During embryonic development, RGC axons navigate with remarkable precision to reach their appropriate targets in either the ipsilateral or contralateral hemisphere. This binary routing decision is made at the optic chiasm and is controlled by tightly regulated transcriptional programs. The zinc-finger transcription factor *Zic2* plays a central role in this process by specifying ipsilateral RGC identity and activating downstream signaling pathways—including Eph receptors and Wnt signaling—that confer sensitivity to midline repulsive cues such as ephrinB2 and Wnt5a^{14–16}. Through this program, embryonic RGC growth cones acquire the

intrinsic competence required to interpret environmental guidance information and execute selective navigation decisions.

Whether similar guidance competence can be reinstated during regeneration in the adult CNS remains unclear. Although several studies have shown that guidance cues persist in the adult visual pathway and can influence regenerating axons^{6,10,11} mature neurons are generally thought to lack the intrinsic capacity to engage developmental guidance programs. This loss of competence may reflect changes in transcriptional state or chromatin organization associated with neuronal maturation, potentially limiting access of developmental transcription factors to their target gene networks.

Here, we asked whether reactivation of a defined developmental transcriptional program is sufficient to restore guidance competence in regenerating adult neurons. Using adeno-associated virus-mediated expression of *Zic2* in adult RGCs following optic nerve injury, we tested whether reinstating a developmental identity factor can bias axon trajectory at a major choice point. We show that *Zic2* reactivation induces guidance receptor expression, restores responsiveness to midline cues that persist in the adult environment, and redirects regenerating axons toward the ipsilateral optic tract. Together, these findings reveal that adult neurons retain a latent intrinsic competence that can be re-engaged to control axon navigation during regeneration, identifying trajectory specification as a reprogrammable dimension of CNS repair.

METHODS

Mice

Conditional *Pten*^{fl/fl} mice were derived from the strain BRaf CA; *Pten* loxP; Tyr::CreER T2 (Jackson #013590). DBA1–C57BL/6 mice were maintained in the IN animal facility. All the animal procedures were approved by the regional Animal Care and Use Committee (2020/VSC/PEA/0235) and met the European (2013/63/UE) and Spanish regulations (RD 53/2013).

AAV2-injections into the retina and Optic Nerve Crush (ONC)

Adult (4–6-week-old) mice were anesthetized with isoflurane and received an intravitreal injection of a mixture of CreAAV2 and CNTFAAV2, followed 24 h later by an injection of c-mycAAV2. Two weeks later, optic nerve (ON) crush was performed in the injected eye. Briefly, mice were anesthetized by intraperitoneal injection of ketamine (100 mg/kg) and medetomidine (0.5 mg/kg), and received subcutaneous analgesia (buprenorphine). The ON was surgically exposed under an operating microscope and crushed 1 mm behind the eyeball for 5 sec using Dumont #5 inverted forceps. Human IL6AAV2 alone or together with Zic2AAV2 were injected intravitreally immediately after ONC. AAV2 CAG-EGFP and AAV2 CAG-EGFP-Cre were purchased to VVF (ETH Zürich). pAAV2 CNTF and pAA2V c-myc constructs were generously donated by Zhigang He (Harvard University, US). pAAV2-Zic2 construct was produced by cloning human Zic2¹⁴ at EcoRI/BamHI sites of the pAAV2 plasmid. AAV2 particles encoding CNTF, AAV2 c-myc and Zic2 were produced at the Neurotropic Vectors Unit of the IN (<https://in.umh-csic.es/en/the-institute/services/neurotropic-vectors/>). AAV2 hyper-IL6 was prepared as described in¹⁷. The titer of the AAV2s ranged from 1.1-1.7 x 10E12 vg/ml. Animals recovered from anesthesia in individual cages and received a subcutaneous injection of atipamezole. All intravitreal injections were performed in a volume of 1.5 µl per virus. Two days before analysis, 1–2 µl of Alexa Fluor 555–labeled cholera toxin subunit B (CTB-555) was injected intravitreally into the ONC eye.

Immunofluorescence and RGC soma quantification in whole mount retinas

Retinas dissected from perfused mice were permeabilized and blocked using fetal bovine serum 1%, Gelatin 0.02% and Triton X-100 0.1% and incubated with Anti-GFP (chicken 1:1000, Aves Labs), anti-Pou4f1 (mouse, 1:300, Millipore), anti-βCatenin (mouse 1:500; BD Transduction Labs), anti-panEph (mouse, 1:300)¹⁸ and anti-Zic2 (rabbit, 1:500)¹⁹ overnight at 4°C. Alexa-Fluor secondary antibodies (1:400, Thermo Fisher) and Dapi were used. Retinas were mounted in flat-mount using Mowiol and coverslips were sealed with nail polish. Five or six equivalent areas were imaged per retina with a confocal microscope Olympus FV1200 with a 20x Oil objective, using constant laser settings and a z-interval of 5 micra. For colocalization and density measurements in the retina surface, somas were counted in 4-5 equivalent 0.1 mm²-squared areas per retina and the colocalization percentage or total density calculated.

Colocalization percentages and density values were averaged first per retina and then per experimental group.

In utero electroporation and embryonic retinal explant cultures

Time-pregnant wild-type DBA1–C57BL/6 females at embryonic day 13.5 (E13.5) were anesthetized and in utero electroporation (IUE) was performed as previously described²⁰. pCAG-GFP and pCAG-Zic2 plasmids were injected into the embryonic eye at 0.5 µg/µl and 1µg/µl, respectively. Retinal explants were prepared from electroporated embryos at E14.5 as previously described²¹ and cultured on glass-bottom dishes (MatTek) coated with 0.01% poly-L-lysine and 20 µg/ml laminin and maintained in DMEM/F12 supplemented with B27, penicillin/streptomycin, and 0.4% methylcellulose.

Twenty-four hours after plating, explants were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA), permeabilized with 0.025% Triton X-100, blocked in BSA, and incubated with anti-GFP (chicken, 1:1000; Aves Labs) overnight at 4 °C. Images were acquired using a Leica Thunder Imager inverted microscope equipped with a Leica DFC9000GTC camera. For axon length quantification, images were processed in Fiji, and axons were traced using NeuronJ. Axon lengths were averaged per experimental group.

Stripe assays with adult RGC explants

Stripes assays and adult RGC explants were prepared as previously described^{21,22}. FC recombinant protein (6 mg/ml) of, ephrinB1 or ephrinB2 (R&D system) were mixed with Alexa594-conjugated anti-hFC antibody (Invitrogen) in HBSS for 30 min. Recombinant proteins were injected into matrices (90 mm width) placed on crystal coverslip pre-treated with poly-L-lysine, resulting in red-fluorescent stripes. After 30 min incubation at 37°C, coverslips were washed with HBSS, and matrices carefully removed. The coverslips were further coated with 6 mg/ml of FC protein mixed with anti-hFC (no fluorescent dye) for 30 min at 37°C, washed three times with HBSS and coated with 20 mg/ml of laminin for 2 h at 37°C. Retinal explants from adult *Pten*^{fl/fl} mice (P60) injected with creAAV2 + GFPAAV2 or creAAV2 + Zic2AAV2, 2 weeks before the experiment, were cultured for 10 days-in-vitro (DiV) on the stripes and fixed with 4% PFA in PBS for 20 min at RT, washed and incubated with the mouse monoclonal anti-beta-III

tubulin antibody (mouse 1:1000, Biolegend) and Alexa-488 anti-mouse secondary antibody. The total number of beta-III tubulin pixels on red or black stripes were quantified using Image J and an automatic stripe assay analysis²¹, calculated as repulsion index and represented as fold change in relation to Fc/Fc control stripes²³.

In situ hybridization in adult optic chiasms

E16.5 mouse embryos and P80 adult mice were intracardially perfused with 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA). The tissue was cryoprotected in 30% (w/v) sucrose in PBS and frozen in dry ice. Coronal and horizontal sections (35 μ m) were obtained with a cryostat (Leica) and stored at -20° C until used. ISH was performed according to previously reported methods²⁴. To detect Wnt5a (NM_009524.4; 1143 to 2166 bp) and ephrinB2 specific antisense riboprobes were used (gift of Ethan David, University of Rochester, NY, USA and S Williams, University of North Carolina, USA, respectively). Images were captured with a Leica DM2500 microscope equipped with a Leica DFC7000T camera.

iDISCO brain clearing and quantification of regenerating axons

Mice were anesthetized and transcardially perfused with PBS followed by 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA). Brains with the attached optic nerves (ONs) and eyes were carefully dissected and post-fixed in 4% PFA overnight at 4 °C. Tissue clearing was performed using the iDISCO protocol²⁵. Briefly, optic chiasm preparations with attached ONs were dehydrated in methanol and cleared with dichloromethane followed by benzyl ether. Samples were subsequently transferred to ethyl cinnamate for refractive index matching and imaged on an Ultramicroscope II (LaVision BioTec) using a z-step of 1 μ m. Optic chiasm z-stacks were 3D reconstructed, and CTB-labeled axons were manually traced using arivis Vision4D (Zeiss).

To quantify axon entry into the optic chiasm, individual CTB-labeled axons crossing an imaginary line drawn perpendicular to the ON at the chiasm entry point were counted in each experimental group. The midline was used as the reference boundary to classify axons as ipsilateral (remaining in the hemisphere of the injected ON and projecting toward the ipsilateral optic tract), contralateral (crossing the midline and extending into the opposite hemisphere), or

retino-retinal (entering the contralateral ON). Axons that did not reach the midline, or that approached the midline but displayed ambiguous trajectories, were excluded from the analysis. For the ipsilateral tract analysis, only ipsilateral axons extending >1 mm beyond the chiasm were included.

Statistical analysis

Male and female mice were randomly assigned to experimental groups. Statistical significance between two groups was assessed using an unpaired two-tailed Student's t-test. For comparisons involving more than two groups, one-way ANOVA was performed followed by Bonferroni's or Tukey's multiple-comparisons test, as indicated in the figure legends. Analyses and data visualization were conducted using RStudio and GraphPad Prism.

For stripe assays, data are presented as box-and-whisker plots, where the central line denotes the median, the box represents the interquartile range (25th–75th percentiles), and whiskers indicate the minimum and maximum values. Sample sizes (n) and exact P values are reported in the figure legends. A P value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Unless otherwise stated, data are shown as mean \pm s.e.m.

RESULTS

Zic2 expression in RGCs regrowing after axotomy slows down axon growth

To promote retinal ganglion cell (RGC) axon regrowth in adult mice after optic nerve (ON) injury, we injected PTEN conditional mice intravitreally with an AAV2 cocktail encoding Cre recombinase, CNTF, and c-Myc (AAV2s)⁴. Two weeks later, we performed monocular optic nerve crush (ONC) and delivered AAV2-hyper-IL6 to further boost axon regeneration¹⁷. To test a potential effect of Zic2 in the trajectories of regrowing axons, we injected an AAV2 encoding Zic2 (Zic2AAV2) together with AAV2-IL6. At 28 days post-crush (dpc), the axonal tracer Cholera Toxin Subunit B conjugated to Alexa Fluor 555 (CTB-555) was also injected in the axotomized eye, and animals were sacrificed and processed for analysis the following day (**Fig. 1A, B**). As previously reported, AAV2 retinal injections displayed high RGC tropism and RGC-targeting efficiency (56 \pm 1.9% of GFP cells were Pou4f1-positive and 40 \pm 1.1% of Pou4f1 cells were GFP-positive). Zic2 expression was detected in 35 \pm 19% of Pou4f1 cells in the Zic2AAV2-

injected retinas, contrasting with retinas infected with control AAV2s that did not express Zic2 (**Fig. 1C, D**). We assessed whether Zic2 expression in RGCs interferes with the previously reported AAV2-mediated neuroprotective strategy^{3,4,17}. After ONC, the number of neuronal cell bodies was similar in retinas infected with AAV2s alone and in those co-infected with AAV2s + Zic2AAV2 (**Fig. 1E, F**), indicating that Zic2 neither confers neuroprotection nor promotes neurodegeneration under these conditions.

Next, we used CTB labeling of RGC axons and imaging of cleared brain tissue to quantify the entry of regenerating axons into the optic chiasm. At 28 dpc, axons from retinas injected with AAV2s had already reached the chiasm, whereas mice receiving AAV2s plus Zic2AAV2 displayed fewer regenerating axons at the chiasm entry (**Fig. 1G, H**). Because whole-mount retinal analysis showed that Zic2 does not induce RGC loss (**Fig. 1E, F**), we reasoned that Zic2 may instead compromise RGC axonal outgrowth.

To test this hypothesis and determine whether Zic2 also affects developing axons, we introduced Zic2-encoding plasmids into the retinas of E13.5 mouse embryos by in utero electroporation and assessed axon extension from retinal explants in culture (**Fig. 1I**). Consistent with the in vivo results in adult RGCs, axons from Zic2-expressing explants were significantly shorter than those from control explants (**Fig. 1J, K**), while the number of axons emerging from the explant was comparable between conditions. Together, these findings indicate that Zic2 delays—rather than blocks—axon growth in both developing and adult RGCs, in vivo and in vitro.

Zic2 induces the expression of guidance cues receptors in adult RGCs

We next wondered whether the expression of Zic2 in the adult retina is capable of upregulating membrane receptors such as EphB1 or Fz, as it does during development^{15,16}. Immunohistochemical analysis using pan-Eph receptors and β catenin antibodies in adult wholemount retinas injected with AAV2s or AAV2s plus Zic2AAV2 showed a significant increase of cells positive for Eph and β catenin (**Fig. 2A-C**). These results suggest that, as in embryonic RGCs, Zic2 is able to induce the expression of Eph and Wnt receptors in adult RGCs

To assess whether Zic2 expression modifies the responsiveness of adult RGC axons to midline-repulsive cues, we performed stripe assay experiments using retinal explants prepared from

adult $Pten^{fl/fl}$ mice infected with either AAV2s or Zic2AAV2 + AAV2s. Retinal explants were cultured on alternating stripes coated with ephrinB2, or ephrinB1 and control substrates. The analysis of stripes assays revealed that Zic2-expressing RGC axons were selectively repelled by ephrinB2, while displaying no significant avoidance of ephrinB1 or control substrates (**Fig. 2D-F**). These results indicated that Zic2 is sufficient to confer ephrinB2-mediated repulsive sensitivity to adult RGC axons, recapitulating a key guidance property during developmental optic chiasm navigation.

Next, we aimed to investigate whether guidance cues associated with midline repulsion during development remain expressed in the adult optic chiasm. We performed *in situ* hybridization for Wnt5a and ephrinB2 mRNAs on sections from adult mice as well coronal sections from E15.5 embryos at the level of the optic chiasm as a control (**Fig. 2G**). As expected, both Wnt5a and ephrinB2 showed robust expression at the midline during embryonic stages, consistent with their established roles in directing axonal divergence throughout optic chiasm formation. Although with a more restricted pattern compared to embryos, the adult tissue showed persistent expression of both of these molecules at the midline region of the optic chiasm. These results indicate that key midline repulsive cues are maintained in the adult optic pathway, suggesting that this molecular environment may influence axonal regrowing after injury.

Zic2 expression in regenerating adult RGCs biases axonal trajectories toward the ipsilateral optic tract

These results encouraged us to analyze the trajectories of regrowing RGC axons at the optic chiasm of AAV2cre-injected and AAV2cre plus Zic2AAV2-injected $Pten^{fl/fl}$ mice. We used the midline as a dividing border to sort the axons into ipsilateral, contralateral or retino-retinal categories. The latest category referring to those axons regrowing into the contralateral optic nerve. Remarkably, axotomized mice injected with AAV2s plus Zic2AAV2 exhibited a very significant increase in the proportion of ipsilaterally-oriented RGC axons at the optic chiasm level and a concomitant decrease in contralateral-oriented axons, compared to the control group (**Fig. 3A, B**). We also quantified the RGC axons penetrating the optic tract, observing a higher proportion of regenerative axons in the ipsilateral tract of mice injected with AAV2s + Zic2AAV2 compared to the controls (**Fig. 3C**). Considering that just ~40% of the RGCs of the

retina injected with the Zic2AAV2 express Zic2 (**Fig. 1C, D**), our results strongly suggest that Zic2 upregulation in adult axotomized RGCs is sufficient to efficiently trigger midline avoidance of regrowing axons at the optic chiasm.

In summary, this study demonstrates that a single transcription factor that controls particular axon trajectories during embryonic development is able to effectively reproduce such trajectories in regenerating axons of damaged adult mice.

DISCUSSION

Axon regeneration in the adult central nervous system has largely been framed as a problem of insufficient growth capacity. Although recent strategies have demonstrated that adult neurons can be induced to regrow axons over long distances, these advances have also highlighted a persistent limitation: regenerating axons frequently fail to navigate appropriately at key decision points. In this study, we address this challenge by asking whether trajectory specification itself can be reinstated during adult axon regeneration. We show that ectopic expression of the developmental transcription factor Zic2 in adult regenerating retinal ganglion cells is sufficient to bias axon navigation toward the ipsilateral optic tract after optic nerve injury, demonstrating that developmental guidance decisions can be reimposed in the injured adult CNS.

Zic2 expression slows axonal extension both in adult regenerating RGCs *in vivo* and in embryonic retinal explants *in vitro*, suggesting that growth dynamics and trajectory selection may be mechanistically coupled. During development, Zic2 regulates intracellular pathways that influence cytoskeletal organization and growth cone behavior¹⁶, and its reactivation in adult neurons may impose a guidance-competent state characterized by reduced growth speed. Such a state may favor accurate interpretation of environmental cues over maximal extension, highlighting a potential trade-off between growth rate and navigational precision that operates during both development and regeneration.

Consistent with its developmental role, Zic2 induces the expression of Eph receptors and promotes β -catenin accumulation in adult RGCs, reinstating a molecular signature characteristic of ipsilaterally projecting embryonic neurons¹⁴⁻¹⁶. This transcriptional response indicates that adult RGCs retain the ability to engage a Zic2-dependent gene regulatory program, implying that the chromatin landscape of mature neurons remains permissive for the activation of

guidance-related transcriptional modules. Thus, rather than requiring large-scale epigenetic reconfiguration, developmental transcription factors appear capable of operating within a pre-existing state of latent competence in adult neurons. This reprogramming is accompanied by a selective repulsive response to ephrinB2, but not ephrinB1, demonstrating that Zic2 is sufficient to restore sensitivity to specific midline repellents in mature neurons. Together, these findings indicate that the intracellular machinery required to decode ephrinB2-mediated guidance cues is not irreversibly silenced after maturation, but can be re-engaged when appropriate transcriptional inputs are restored.

In parallel, we find that ephrinB2 and Wnt5a, two major midline repellents during optic chiasm development, remain expressed at the adult midline, albeit at lower levels than during embryogenesis. The persistence of these ligands suggests that the adult optic chiasm retains instructive molecular features capable of influencing regenerating axons. In this context, guidance failure after injury may arise not from the absence of extracellular information, but from a mismatch between persistent environmental cues and a loss of intrinsic competence to interpret them. Our results support the idea that restoring transcriptional competence can realign regenerating axons with an instructive environment that is already in place.

Together, our data support a conceptual framework in which axon trajectory specification represents a dimension of regeneration that is separable from axon growth and is constrained by the competence state of the neuron. From this perspective, regenerative failure reflects not only limited extension, but also a failure to access appropriate gene regulatory programs at critical decision points. Developmental transcriptional programs therefore provide a means to instruct regeneration by reinstating selective navigation states, rather than by further amplifying growth alone. Achieving functional repair will ultimately require precise control of both trajectory specification and long-distance navigation^{12,26}. Although our study focuses on a single transcription factor and a specific choice point in the visual pathway, the conceptual implications extend beyond this system. Identifying transcriptional programs that bias alternative trajectories, such as contralateral routing, will be an important next step. In this regard, members of the Pou family of transcription factors, which regulate decussation of visual axons during development^{27,28} represent promising candidates. More broadly, it will be important to determine how the adult chromatin landscape constrains or enables access to distinct guidance programs,

and whether different neuronal populations retain comparable degrees of latent competence. Moreover, while our results demonstrate robust control of axon trajectories at the midline, future work will be required to determine whether regenerating axons can be guided across multiple decision points to reach their appropriate target nuclei and establish functional synaptic connections.

In conclusion, our findings reveal that adult regenerating neurons retain a previously underappreciated state of developmental competence that permits the reactivation of guidance-related transcriptional programs. By demonstrating that a single developmental transcription factor can reimpose trajectory decisions in the injured adult CNS, this work identifies guidance competence as a property encoded, at least in part, in the adult chromatin landscape, and highlights a conceptual avenue for achieving greater precision in regenerative repair.

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. Ectopic expression of Zic2 in adult RGCs regrowing after axotomy slows down axon growth.

(A) Experimental timeline. dpi, days post injection; dpc, days post crush; ONC, optic nerve crush.

(B) Schematic overview of the experimental design (C) Representative immunostaining of AAV2-injected retinal flat-mounts for Pou4f1 (RGC marker). Zic2 is not endogenously expressed in adult mouse RGCs in retinas injected with AAV2s alone. Scale bar, 50 μ m.

(D) Quantification of RGC tropism (light gray) and RGC-targeting efficiency (dark gray). N= 1646 GFP / 2781 Pou4f1 cells in 3 wt mice; 717 Zic2 / 1156 Pou4f1 cells, in 2 wt mice. (E,F)

RGC survival after 28 dpc in Pten^{fl/fl} mice injected with AAV2s or AAV2s + AAV2Zic2. (E) Representative whole-mount retinas stained for TUJ1 to label RGC somata. Scale bar, 50 μ m.

(F) Density of Tuj1-labelled RGC somas. N= 2906 cells in naïve retinas (4 mice); 622 cells in injured control retinas (4 mice); 1,092 cells in injured AAV2s-infected retinas (4 mice); 1,243 cells in injured AAV2s + Zic2AAV2-infected retinas (3 mice). (G,H) Regenerating CTB-labeled

RGC axons at the optic chiasm in injured Pten^{fl/fl} mice injected with AAV2s or AAV2s + Zic2AAV2 (28 dpc). (G) Representative 3D reconstruction of the optic chiasm entry showing

CTB-labeled axons. Scale bar, 200 μ m. (H) Number of CTB-labeled axons entering the optic chiasm. N = 219 axons from 9 AAV2s-injected mice; 118 axons from 11 AAV2s + Zic2AAV2-

injected mice. (I–K) Retinal explants from E13.5 embryos electroporated with GFP or GFP/Zic2 plasmids. (J) Representative GFP-RGC axons extending from retinal explants after 48 h in culture. Scale bar, 50 μ m. (K) Axon length quantification. N = 488 and 305 axons from 38 GFP

explants and 33 GFP/Zic2 explants, respectively, pooled from six independent cultures. Statistics: one-way ANOVA Bonferroni's multiple-comparisons test (^{##}p < 0.01; n.s., not significant). Unpaired two-tailed Student's *t*-test (*P* < 0.05, ***p* < 0.001).

Figure 2. Zic2 induces receptors for midline repulsive cues expressed in the adult optic chiasm.

(A) Confocal images of flat-mounted retinas infected with AAV2s or AAV2 + Zic2AAV2 showing Eph receptors and β catenin expression at 28 dpi. Scale bar, 50 μ m. (B-C). Density of Eph-positive cells (B) and β catenin-positive cells (C) in retinas infected with AAV2s + Zic2AAV2 compared with AAV2s-infected retinas. N= 71 and 2131 Eph-positive cells in 6 AAV2s and 7 Zic2AAV2-infected mice, respectively. 24 and 945 β -catenin-positive cells in 5 AAV2s and 5 Zic2AAV2-infected mice, respectively. (D) Experimental graphical design. Retinal explants from $Pten^{fl/fl}$; Rosa26-TdTomato mice infected with creAAV2 or creAAV2 + Zic2AAV2 were dissected 14 dpi and cultured on stripes coated with ephrinB1, ephrinB2, or control substrates during 10 DiV. (E) Representative images of RGC axons from retinal explants labelled with the axonal marker Tuj1 regrowing over strips coated with the indicated molecules in both experimental groups. Inverted color masks of axons (blue) and ephrinB1/B2 or control substrate-coated stripes (reddish) are shown next to each image for clarity. Scale bar, 50 μ m. (F) Quantification of stripe assay experiments showing that axons of Zic2-expressing RGCs are repelled by ephrinB2, but not by ephrinB1 or control substrates. Each dot in the boxplots represents the percentage of pixels (axons) on red stripes. N= 15-58 explants/condition from 3 independent experiments. (G) *In situ* hybridization for Wnt5a and ephrinB2 on coronal sections of E15.5 embryos at the optic chiasm level and on coronal and horizontal sections from adult (P70-80) mice. N= 4 mice for the Wnt5a probe; N= 5 mice for the ephrinB2 probe. Arrowheads mark mRNA expression at the optic chiasm. ON, optic nerve. Scale bars: 200 μ m. Unpaired two-tailed Student's *t*-test ** $p < 0.01$. One-way ANOVA Tukey's multiple comparisons test ### $p < 0.001$, n.s., not significant.

Figure 3. Expression of Zic2 in regenerative adult RGCs biases axonal trajectories toward the ipsilateral optic tract.

(A) 3D reconstructions and tracings of CTB-labelled RGC axons regrowing at the optic chiasm of injured $Pten^{fl/fl}$ mice injected with AAV2s or AAV2s + Zic2AAV2 at 28 dpc. Scale bar, 200 μ m. (B) Quantification of RGC axon trajectories classified as Contralateral (Contra), Ipsilateral (Ipsi) and Retino –Retinal (R-R) in each experimental group. N= 196 axons, 5 AAV2s-injected mice; 149 axons, 5 AAV2s + Zic2AAV2-injected mice. (C) Quantification of ipsilateral RGC axons entering the ipsilateral optic tract (green tracings, white arrowheads). Only axons extending

beyond the 1-mm line traced from the optic nerves (yellow line) were scored as entering the ipsilateral tract. Axons not reaching 1 mm depth from optic nerves were excluded (dark tracings). One-way ANOVA Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test *** $p < 0.0001$. n.s., not significant. Unpaired two-tailed Student's *t*-test * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, n.s., not significant.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT to improve the English. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

REFERENCES

1. Laha, B., Stafford, B.K., and Huberman, A.D. (2017). Regenerating optic pathways from the eye to the brain. *Science* 356, 1031–1034. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aal5060>.
2. Mason, C., and Slavi, N. (2020). Retinal Ganglion Cell Axon Wiring Establishing the Binocular Circuit. *Annu. Rev. Vis. Sci.* 6, 215–236. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-vision-091517-034306>.
3. Sun, F., Park, K.K., Belin, S., Wang, D., Lu, T., Chen, G., Zhang, K., Yeung, C., Feng, G., Yankner, B.A., et al. (2011). Sustained axon regeneration induced by co-deletion of PTEN and SOCS3. *Nature* 480, 372–375. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature10594>.

4. Belin, S., Nawabi, H., Wang, C., Tang, S., Latremoliere, A., Warren, P., Schorle, H., Uncu, C., Woolf, C.J., He, Z., et al. (2015). Injury-Induced Decline of Intrinsic Regenerative Ability Revealed by Quantitative Proteomics. *Neuron* 86, 1000–1014.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2015.03.060>.
5. Vilallongue, N., Schaeffer, J., Hesse, A.-M., Delpech, C., Blot, B., Paccard, A., Plissonnier, E., Excoffier, B., Couté, Y., Belin, S., et al. (2022). Guidance landscapes unveiled by quantitative proteomics to control reinnervation in adult visual system. *Nat Commun* 13, 6040. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-33799-4>.
6. Delpech, C., Schaeffer, J., Vilallongue, N., Delaunay, A., Benadjal, A., Blot, B., Excoffier, B., Plissonnier, E., Gascon, E., Albert, F., et al. (2024). Axon guidance during mouse central nervous system regeneration is required for specific brain innervation. *Dev Cell* 59, 3213-3228.e8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.devcel.2024.09.005>.
7. Lim, J.-H.A., Stafford, B.K., Nguyen, P.L., Lien, B.V., Wang, C., Zukor, K., He, Z., and Huberman, A.D. (2016). Neural activity promotes long-distance, target-specific regeneration of adult retinal axons. *Nat Neurosci* 19, 1073–1084. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.4340>.
8. Varadarajan, S.G., Wang, F., Dhande, O.S., Le, P., Duan, X., and Huberman, A.D. (2023). Postsynaptic neuronal activity promotes regeneration of retinal axons. *Cell Rep* 42, 112476. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2023.112476>.
9. F, B., Hhc, L., X, L., G, G., H, J., L, M., C, W., L, H., Tk, H., E, F., et al. (2016). Restoration of Visual Function by Enhancing Conduction in Regenerated Axons. *Cell* 164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2015.11.036>.
10. Pernet, V., Joly, S., Dalkara, D., Jordi, N., Schwarz, O., Christ, F., Schaffer, D.V., Flannery, J.G., and Schwab, M.E. (2013). Long-distance axonal regeneration induced by CNTF gene transfer is impaired by axonal misguidance in the injured adult optic nerve. *Neurobiology of Disease* 51, 202–213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbd.2012.11.011>.
11. Pernet, V., Joly, S., Jordi, N., Dalkara, D., Guzik-Kornacka, A., Flannery, J.G., and Schwab, M.E. (2013). Misguidance and modulation of axonal regeneration by Stat3 and Rho/ROCK

- signaling in the transparent optic nerve. *Cell Death Dis* 4, e734–e734.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/cddis.2013.266>.
12. Yang, S.-G., Li, C.-P., Peng, X.-Q., Teng, Z.-Q., Liu, C.-M., and Zhou, F.-Q. (2020). Strategies to Promote Long-Distance Optic Nerve Regeneration. *Front. Cell. Neurosci.* 14, 119. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncel.2020.00119>.
 13. Murcia-Belmonte, V., and Erskine, L. (2019). Wiring the Binocular Visual Pathways. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 20, 3282. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms20133282>.
 14. Herrera, E., Brown, L., Aruga, J., Rachel, R.A., Dolen, G., Mikoshiba, K., Brown, S., and Mason, C.A. (2003). *Zic2* patterns binocular vision by specifying the uncrossed retinal projection. *Cell* 114, 545–557. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0092-8674\(03\)00684-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0092-8674(03)00684-6).
 15. García-Frigola, C., Carreres, M.I., Vegar, C., Mason, C., and Herrera, E. (2008). *Zic2* promotes axonal divergence at the optic chiasm midline by EphB1-dependent and -independent mechanisms. *Development* 135, 1833–1841.
<https://doi.org/10.1242/dev.020693>.
 16. Morenilla-Palao, C., López-Cascales, M.T., López-Atalaya, J.P., Baeza, D., Calvo-Díaz, L., Barco, A., and Herrera, E. (2020). A *Zic2*-regulated switch in a noncanonical Wnt/ β catenin pathway is essential for the formation of bilateral circuits. *Sci Adv* 6, eaaz8797.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aaz8797>.
 17. Leibinger, M., Andreadaki, A., Gobrecht, P., Levin, E., Diekmann, H., and Fischer, D. (2016). Boosting Central Nervous System Axon Regeneration by Circumventing Limitations of Natural Cytokine Signaling. *Molecular Therapy* 24, 1712–1725.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/mt.2016.102>.
 18. Jevince, A.R., Kadison, S.R., Pittman, A.J., Chien, C.-B., and Kaprielian, Z. (2006). Distribution of EphB receptors and ephrin-B1 in the developing vertebrate spinal cord. *J Comp Neurol* 497, 734–750. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cne.21001>.

19. Murillo, B., Ruiz-Reig, N., Herrera, M., Fairén, A., and Herrera, E. (2015). Zic2 Controls the Migration of Specific Neuronal Populations in the Developing Forebrain. *J Neurosci* 35, 11266–11280. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0779-15.2015>.
20. Garcia-Frigola, C., Carreres, M.I., Vegar, C., and Herrera, E. (2007). Gene delivery into mouse retinal ganglion cells by in utero electroporation. *BMC Dev Biol* 7, 103. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-213X-7-103>.
21. Murcia-Belmonte, V., Chauvin, G., Coca, Y., Escalante, A., Klein, R., and Herrera, E. (2025). EphA4 Mediates EphrinB1-Dependent Adhesion in Retinal Ganglion Cells. *J Neurosci* 45, e0043242024. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0043-24.2024>.
22. Schaeffer, J., Delpech, C., Albert, F., Belin, S., and Nawabi, H. (2020). Adult Mouse Retina Explants: From ex vivo to in vivo Model of Central Nervous System Injuries. *Front Mol Neurosci* 13, 599948. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnmol.2020.599948>.
23. Schneider, C.A., Rasband, W.S., and Eliceiri, K.W. (2012). NIH Image to ImageJ: 25 years of image analysis. *Nat Methods* 9, 671–675. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.2089>.
24. Schaeren-Wiemers, N., and Gerfin-Moser, A. (1993). A single protocol to detect transcripts of various types and expression levels in neural tissue and cultured cells: in situ hybridization using digoxigenin-labelled cRNA probes. *Histochemistry* 100, 431–440. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00267823>.
25. Renier, N., Wu, Z., Simon, D.J., Yang, J., Ariel, P., and Tessier-Lavigne, M. (2014). iDISCO: A Simple, Rapid Method to Immunolabel Large Tissue Samples for Volume Imaging. *Cell* 159, 896–910. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2014.10.010>.
26. Giger, R.J., Hollis, E.R., and Tuszynski, M.H. (2010). Guidance molecules in axon regeneration. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Biol* 2, a001867. <https://doi.org/10.1101/cshperspect.a001867>.
27. Fernández-Nogales, M., López-Cascales, M.T., Murcia-Belmonte, V., Escalante, A., Fernández-Albert, J., Muñoz-Viana, R., Barco, A., and Herrera, E. (2022). Multiomic

Analysis of Neurons with Divergent Projection Patterns Identifies Novel Regulators of Axon Pathfinding. *Adv Sci (Weinh)* 9, e2200615. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adv.202200615>.

28. Fries, M., Brown, T.W., Jolicoeur, C., Boulan, B., Boudreau-Pinsonneault, C., Javed, A., Abram, P., and Cayouette, M. (2023). Pou3f1 orchestrates a gene regulatory network controlling contralateral retinogeniculate projections. *Cell Rep* 42, 112985. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2023.112985>.

Figure 1

Figure 2

A

AAV2s

AAV2s + Zic2AAV2

Figure 3